

Paper 6

IMPLEMENTATION OF DATA ANALYTICS IN POWER SECTOR USING SMART GRID TECHNOLOGY – A CASE STUDY ON KARNATAKA POWER TRANSMISSION CONTROL LIMITED (KPTCL)

K. Vikranth^{1, 2} & Krishna Prasad K³

¹Research Scholar, College of Computer Science and Information science, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science, Vivekananda College, Puttur, India

³College of Computer Science & Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India

Email: vikranth.kadya@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Power sector is one of the industry contains huge number of customers as well as huge number of employees are working on different category that required for the smooth operation of the power sector industry. It has to adopt new technologies to improve its operations both in business as well as technical side to provide better service to huge number of customers. Karnataka Power Transmission Corporation Limited (KPTCL) is a power supply and transportation company in Karnataka state established in the year of 1999 beneath the company act 1956. Now it is one of the big government company owned by government of Karnataka with 1000 Crores of share capital. The ultimate goal of KPTCL is to provide uninterrupted power supply to all customers in state of Karnataka with minimum distribution and transmission cost and lowest unit price. Power generation is not a big deal for any state government but real challenge is to transmission and distribution of uninterrupted electricity to different parts of the state using power grid. So there should be proper data analysis in the entire grid and all transmission station throughout the state in order to identify the loop holes, actual capacity, requirement, request from consumers, and also to identify any damages. The ultimate solution for all this is introduction of smart grid concept in power grid. In this paper I reviewed about factors to be considered while performing data analytics in power grid and adoption of smart grid concept over traditional grid using SCADA technology to perform data analytics and finally listed out some improvements in overall functioning of KPTCL after implementation of smart grid.

Keywords: smart grid, KPTCL, transmission, distribution, smart meter, transmitter, SCADA, PMU, BDA.

1. INTRODUCTION:

KPTCL is power transmission and Distribution Company owned by government of Karnataka which is the only company in Karnataka state which is domination in the sector. It

should have proper network configuration to transmit and distribute the electricity to various parts of the state. Distribution and transmission network contains different components like power stations, sub stations, power grids, transformers, power meters, station meters etc. the production, transmission and distribution are separate units because of that there is a huge gap between these units. Here transmission and distribution units facing lot of problems, result of that there is a huge power loss, black holes, load problems etc. [21]. To overcome from such situation there should be automation in power sector that can be implemented using Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) [1]. The main operating concern of KPTCL was to maintaining security, quality of power, reliability, and giving stable power and to ensure economically good operation. It can't fulfill this using only the man power, so it requires fully automated and computerized solution that is SCADA. Karnataka government and KPTCL implemented this technology so that from last 12 decades there are no single black holes in state of Karnataka [1]. Also KPTCL distributes authentic and efficient power supply to its entire consumer. One can also examine the data using SCADA while it stores the data, list station or in corporate office one can easily analyze those data and he can sort out the problem. Big data analytics (BDA) is one of the powerful technique used in large consumer based industry like power industry helps to take decision in different dimensions in terms of business aspect as well as consumer side [2]. Especially in power sector there is an limitless opportunities for BDA to provide feedback loop from one substation to another substation or one office to another office which enhances the planning as well as accurate realization of some critical problems which leads to take good decisions and leads to conduct some informed operations.

2. A BIG DATA IN POWER SECTOR:

The 3 V factors of big data are volume, velocity and variety will be generated by various components in power distribution and transmission network.

Volume: The volume of the data usually we restrained in terms of Giga Byte (GB) or Tera Byte (TB) or Peta Byte (PB). The data may be generated from the customer side like customer's feedback or customer's complaints or customer's queries, customer's request etc. also data will be generated from social media, electronic media, print media etc. Advanced meter reading (AMI) will collect data by meter reading from millions of customers all across the Karnataka. Smart meters and Phasor measurement units (PMU) contains sensors that will generate data related to different issue in every second or every time intervals [5]. Millions of such sensors are connected across the power grid and imagine the amount of data that sensors are possible to generate.

Fig. 1: The volume of the data generated by multiple components in power sector. Velocity: Velocity of the data is nothing but how fast the data will be generated and transmitted across the power network or one grid to another grid. There are three types of data with respect to velocity called batch data, online data and stream data. Data generation and transformation will happen during planning process, capacity management process, cyber security assessment process, event analysis, market and trading process and from customer side. The mainstream of power system sensors are event triggered, these sensors will produce data when specific event has been happened in the system

Fig.2: Different components that causes velocity of data generation and transmission. Variety: In modern smart grid technology variety of data comes from different sources. Different sources are smart meters, substation meters, voltmeters, fault detectors etc. smart meter reads the total amount of units consumed by the consumer. Like this various meters and sensors will produce different varieties of data depends on functionality [25].

Fig. 3: Illustrates the varieties of data generated in power sector.

3. A BIG DATA ANALYTICS IN POWER GRID:

Data analytics is possible in power grid in different aspects such as

- Outage management: there was huge power loss in old system, but after implementation of smart grid, through data analysis there it was possible to manage the power outage. Power outage is drastically reduced after implementation of smart grid using SCADA and PMU in power grid [12].
- Consumer behavior: It was possible to predict the behavior of power consumer, in which particular season of the year or which particular time of the day consumer consumes more power. Also can able to forecast which portion of the state consumer consumes more power, so that company can able to manage such situation, so consumer gets stable power supply from the company.

- c. Demand/ Capacity: In some situation few substation demands for more power that is automatically intimated to the grid also it will analyze whether the transmission line have enough capacity to accommodate more power that it demands for. If it possible to supply more power than only they supply more power based on the demand requirement without any damage. All these technical aspects of the operation of power sector are effortlessly achieved with the assistance of data analytics in smart grid technology [14].
- d. Workforce management: Due to availability of data in all the offices of KPTCL, it was easy job for officers to allocate work for employees. After analyzing the data officers can able to know the place where some defects occurred, so it can be managed by allocating some work force to that place and can easily handle.
- e. Energy Theft: Energy theft is the biggest problem in power sector that can be handled after implementation of smart grid. It can able to find which particular transformer or in which substation the energy theft is happening, so company can handle such problems [12].
- f. Crisis management: After implementation of smart grid all these crisis can be managed because it can able to send corresponding warning messages very quickly before or after any such crisis are occurred [5].
- g. Forecasting: Smart grid can also performs data analytics for future needs such as power demands, consumer requirements, line extensions, need of transformers, and need of any other components, whether forecast etc. [23].

4. SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition):

SCADA is the most sophisticated technology used by KPTCL to automate the power system in distribution and transmission network to supply quality power. It will constantly monitor the power system by sending data across the network and MCC (Master Control Centre). The SCADA technology can be categorized in to 3 main areas –

- a. Remote Terminal Units (RTU): It provides analog and digital sensors that have placed across the power network in remote site. Typically it converts electrical signal in to the digital values from various physical equipment that measures voltage, current, pressure, flow, temperature etc.
- b. Communication network: It provides a path way to communicate RTU and Network and Management System (NMS) or master station. Communication network may be wired or wireless communication.
- c. Network Management System (NMS): It contains master stations or sub masters to obtain data from various RTU's through communication network. It provides a user interface to present the data as well as to process the data. There by it manages the remote site where the data was obtained [11].

5. THE HEIRARCHY OF SCADA COMPONETS:

Fig. 5: the hierarchy of various components in SCADA technology

As revealed in figure 5 these are the core 5 components of SCADA system. Here different equipment's or sensors that are placed at remote locations of power grid component. These sensors will be placed in production location, transmission location or distribution or consumer location. Remote Terminal Units (RTU's) are also placed at different locations that receives digital or analog signals from these equipment's and sends the data to master station through the proper communication system. Communication system used by KPTCL is VSAT communication system using satellite. Master stations or different sub master stations having proper software's to receives the data and performs data processing task and displays proper information and automate the task. It contains different data processing systems that processes the different kinds of data based on requirement [39].

6. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF SCADA AT KPTCL:

The SCADA network at KPTCL contains 16 master stations or control centers which includes Main Control Centers (MCC), Disaster Recovery and Management Control centers (DRMCC), Area Load Dispatch Centers (ALDC) for all the ESCOMs. Where transmission RTU is interconnect with MCC1, distribution RTU is interconnect with MCC2, disaster RTU is interconnect with DRMCC and load dispatch RTU is interconnect with ALDC etc. here overall system is designed with seventy two servers and one hundred and fifteen workstations. It uses VSAT communication system having its own network hub and leased line cables for inter center communication [30].

7. VERY SMALL APERTURE TERMINAL (VSAT):

VSAT is main communication media for KPTCL and Electricity Supply Company (ESCOMs) in SCADA network. And also it provides voice communication to all KPTCL, all main stations of ESCOM's such as BESCO, MESCOM, GESCOM, HESCO and major power generation stations with load dispatch center (LDC). VSAT is mainly designed with the purpose of data transmission and distribution over large geographical area [8]. With the help of VSAT, KPTCL monitors, regulates, transmits, processes and delivers the electricity data of above 14.5 million customers and across the Karnataka it covers area around 1,92,000 sq.km. VSAT communication system mainly contains different components such as antenna, Indoor Unit (IDU), Outdoor Unit (ODU), SCADA phone, 8 port switches, Voice over Internet Protocol (VoIP) [19].

8. VSAT CONFIGURATION:

Table 1: The configuration values in different aspects of VSAT communication system

Description	Value
Earth station transmitter antenna gain	52.48db
Satellite transmitter antenna gain	31db
Earth station receiver antenna gain	36.85db
Satellite receiver antenna gain	38.2db
Transponder band width	36 MHz
Up-link frequency band	6.875 – 6.9465 GHz
Down-link frequency band	4.650 – 4.7215 GHz
Up-link loss and down-link loss	221 db -217 db

The frequency and band width values of both satellite and earth station antenna of VSAT communication system are given in the table 1. These are the standards that were set by KPTCL to send and receive data across the network through VSAT communication system [32].

9. CONCLUSION:

KPTCL is the government sector company that serves huge number of customers. For any company or industry has the interest to only satisfy the customers and then making the marginable profit. Such a way KPTCL also achieved this by adopting the new technology to improve its business operation. To accomplish this KPTCL was implemented the SCADA technology and that was the perfect choice to them to overcome all problems. Before implementing SCADA there was huge power loss and black out problems all over the state. KPTCL could not able to find out where was the real problem. But after implementation of SCADA it can easily sorted out all the complications automatically. And there was no single black out in a day after SCADA implementation. Also KPTCL gain big success in all the aspects like business, operational and technical aspect. So the technology reached to greater extent so that it's our determination to use such technology to gain success in any sector. KPTCL successfully proved that by performing data analysis using SCADA technology.

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